

Influence of Classical Frequencies on Quantum Mechanics? (Revised)

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In this brief note, we investigate the role of classical frequencies in quantum mechanical problems. It is known through the correspondence principle that quantum mechanics matches classical physics for high energy levels. It has been shown in previous notes, however, that classical features are already present in all quantum energy levels as the Schrodinger equation may be written as: $(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5m v(x)v(x) = E-V(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. Thus, if there is periodic behaviour associated with $v(x)$, as in an oscillator, it should carry through into the quantum average kinetic energy and potential energy and finally into E , the average energy. This also suggests that the f_p 's ($W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$) are influenced by the classical frequency w .

Classical Oscillator

The one dimensional classical oscillator depends on three parameters: k , m and A the amplitude. The total energy is $.5 k A^2$ and $v_0 = wA$ where $w = \sqrt{k/m}$ the angular frequency, v_0 being the maximum velocity. The classical oscillator problem can be solved to yield $x = A \cos(wt)$ and $v = -Aw \sin(wt)$. The oscillator equation can also be written with A removed i.e.:

$$.5m w^2 \sin^2(wt) + .5k \cos^2(wt) = .5 k$$

It should be noted that in the classical case doubling k doubles energy. If one also doubles mass m , energy doubles, but angular frequency remains unchanged. (This will not be the case for quantum mechanics.)

A point we wish to make is that not only does one have periodicity for x and v , but also for kinetic and potential energy, although it is in the form of $.5m w^2 \sin^2(wt)$ and $.5k \cos^2(wt)$. It seems this idea carries through into quantum mechanics, at least in the ground state of the quantum oscillator.

Association of Classical and Quantum Mechanics

The time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written as:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $v(x)$ is the classical velocity at point x , so the sum over all p 's from minus infinite to infinite multiplied by $p^2/2m$ and $P(p/x) = f_p \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, $W(x)$ is a normalization constant (the wavefunction) is linked directly to classical kinetic energy for any energy level. If $v(x)$ is periodic, it seems this should affect f_p as well as the average kinetic energy and potential energy. The

sum of average kinetic and potential energy should equal the total classical energy, or the average quantum energy.

Alternatively, ((1)) may be written as:

$$(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) ((2))$$

It would be interesting if the periodicity of $v(x)$, namely $\sin(\omega t)$ carried through into the quantum scenario. For the ground state, it appears this is the case. Consider $\exp(-ax^2)$ as a solution. Then, the kinetic energy (left hand side of ((2))), must produce a constant which is energy and a term equivalent to $-.5 k x^2$ because the right hand side of ((2)) is $E-V(x)$. Thus, $4a^2/m = k$ or $a = \sqrt{km}/2$. The energy E becomes $.5 \sqrt{k/m}$ or $.5 \omega$, where ω is the angular frequency. It is interesting to note that doubling k and m in the quantum case does not lead to E doubling, as in the classical one because the wavefunction carries $a = \sqrt{km}/2$. If k and m double, a doubles and causes quantum mechanics to differ.

More generally, one may consider a scenario for which: $d/dx W(x) = g(x) W(x)$. Then, $d/dx d/dx W(x) = [d/dx g(x)] W(x) + g(x)g(x) W(x)$. One equates $(-1 / 2m) g(x)g(x)$ with $-.5k x^2$. Or $g(x) = \pm \sqrt{km} x$ and $(-1/2m) d/dx g(x) = .5 \sqrt{k/m}$. Thus, the ground state energy is proportional to ω . For higher energy states, $d/dx W(x) = g(x) W(x)$ does not hold, but can be modified to obtain an differential equation which applies to Hermite polynomials.

We wish to investigate whether periodicities of kinetic and potential energy $.5m \omega^2 \sin^2(\omega t)$ and $.5k \cos^2(\omega t)$ in classical physics hold in quantum mechanics. Simply obtaining $KE=E-V(x)$ (which satisfies the time-independent Schrodinger equation, does not seem to demonstrate the periodicity clearly, although using the classical time dependence of $v(x)$ as $\sin(\omega t)$ in ((2)) does.

For the oscillator, ((2)) suggests this must be case. Consider the ground state case:

$$(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5 (\sqrt{k/m}) - .5 k x^2 ((3))$$

From the classical case, one has: $x = A \cos(\omega t)$ and $E = .5k A^2$ so:

$x = \sqrt{2E/k} \cos(\omega t)$ and the right hand side of ((3)) becomes:

$$.5(\sqrt{k/m}) - .5 k 2E/k \cos^2(\omega t) = .5 (2E - 2E \cos^2(\omega t)) = E \sin^2(\omega t)$$

Thus, classical periodicity appears to affect quantum mechanics and it seems one could map x into $\sqrt{2E/k} \cos(\omega t)$. Simply working with x in the Schrodinger differential equation does not seem to bring out this dependence on classical frequencies (periodicity) because the time-independent Schrodinger equation does not contain time. Given t , the quantum solution has a factor $\exp(iEt)$ and $E = \hbar \omega (n+.5)$ one sees that there is a relationship between the cycling frequency E and the classical periodicity ω , but ((2)) shows that overall the kinetic and potential energies should be changing in a periodic way.

As a further example of the influence of classical periodicity, consider a change in the quantum density:

$$d/dx [W(x) W(x)] = W(x) W(x) [d/dx W(x)/ W(x)] \quad ((4))$$

It seems there is a flux in quantum mechanics given by $[d/dx W(x)/ W(x)]$.

For the ground state oscillator, this is: $-2 \text{sqrt}(km)/2 x = - x w m$, which is dependent on w .

Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential at the Walls

Consider a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In the classical case, the particle bounces back and forth with a frequency f related to $2L = v (1/f)$. This suggests the classical energy $.5 m v^2 = .5m (2L f)^2$. The quantum solution is of the form $\sin(kx-b)$ where k is the root mean square momentum related to the average energy $(\hbar k)^2/2m$, so k should be linked to a classical frequency.

Cycling

It has been argued in a previous note (1), that one may write the time independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ expressed as Fourier series. This leads to:

$$p^2/2m f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = E f_p \quad ((6))$$

It was suggested this implies a cycling is occurring for each f_p . Different f_k 's scatter off the potential $V(x)$ to create an f_p . The right hand side of ((6)) suggests one may have a time dependence of $\exp(iEt)$. Thus, there is the same time dependence for each f_p . We have argued in this note, that E may be proportional to w , the mechanical frequency in the problem, as in the oscillator case. In quantum mechanics:

$$\text{Average KE} = \sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m f_p^2 \text{ and Average PE} = \sum_{\text{over } p, j} f_p V_j f_{p-j} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, cycling seems to be associated largely with potential energy as plane waves scatter from one state into another to form a resonance with a cycling frequency of $1/E$. For the oscillator $E=\hbar w (n+.5)$ so as n increases, E is close to a multiple of w and $1/E$ becomes smaller and smaller than $1/w$, the classical frequency. Thus, there are two frequencies in the picture, E and w .

In a previous note (2), it was argued that if a plane wave, with momentum k , interacts with a potential $V(x)$ written as a Fourier series, there should be a certain probability for it to collide with V_j , the j th Fourier transform. Given that the momentum from the collision will be $k+j$, one will

obtain f_{k+j} , thus this may be related to the relative probability. In fact, given that V_j carries energy information, one may argue that $\frac{p^2}{2m} f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = \text{constant} f_p$ where $\text{constant}=E$. Thus, different f_k 's may interact with different V_j 's to always form f_p , namely: $\sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k$. It is not only the case that one obtains $E f_p$ on the right hand side of ((6)), it seems the interactions between the f_k 's and V_j 's, must take place over the same cycle time $1/E$ for a quantum bound state resonance to exist and this $1/E$ cycle time must be linked to w .

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that by writing the Schrodinger equation as ((1)) and linking it to $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity at x , classical periodicities in $v(x)$, such as in the oscillator case, influence the quantum mechanical solution. In particular, E may be proportional to w (as well as average quantum KE and PE) and f_p and $W(x)$, the wavefunction are also influenced.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Role of Average Energy and Plane Waves in the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2019)